

Mathematics education in engineering: a triple discontinuity?

Florensa, Ignasi

Escola Universitària Salesiana de Sarrià, Spain

Fraga, Iria

Escola Universitària Salesiana de Sarrià, Spain

Martínez-Junza, Víctor

Escola Universitària Salesiana de Sarrià, Spain

Conference Key Areas: *Mathematics at the heart of Engineering*

Keywords: *Mathematics, Modelling, Engineering*

ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the study of discontinuities in the teaching of mathematics in engineering within the framework of the anthropological theory of didactics (ATD) and, in particular, attempts to characterize the internal discontinuity between the teaching of mathematics and the role of mathematical activity in engineering subjects through an interview campaign with mathematics and engineering teachers. The first step of this research was the work piloting the interview protocol [12]. We now try to improve this protocol to overcome the fact that, even when both engineering and mathematics teachers seem to talk about the same content (solving linear systems, for example), the activity they are addressing is very different. Splitting the interview into two separate parts has allowed us to have a first online questionnaire that gives an explicit introduction about the notions of praxeology, the type of tasks and the technique of ATD to the interviewer and allows him/her to internalize them before conducting the live interview. The first analysis of the results shows that the interviewees are able to describe the mathematical activity (existing and desired) in terms of types of tasks and techniques previously introduced and seems to indicate that there is an important level of consensus on the important contents to be taught in the first year courses. However, some differences appear in the applicationist conception and its justification. Mathematics teachers seem to agree on a conception in which mathematics is a tool to be applied in engineering courses while engineering teachers see mathematics as an intrinsic component of engineering.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Transitions and discontinuities in engineering education

Numerous research works take as object of study phenomena associated to discontinuities and transitions between institutions. For example, there are works addressing the epistemological differences in different courses in engineering schools [1] or others analysing the existing discontinuities in mathematics education [2]. In fact, this field of study is not new: in 1908 Felix Klein announced its famous double discontinuity concerning the professional development of future mathematics teachers [3]. The first discontinuity announced by Klein concerns the transition problems that students experience when they enter at the university, and the second discontinuity relates to the transition between the university and their activity as secondary teachers.

The first discontinuity has been widely addressed, not only in mathematics education but also in engineering education, particularly because of the high level of dropout rates in this field [4] [5]. The second discontinuity in the engineering education - between engineering schools and workplace- has also been extensively addressed and reveals diverse challenges to soften the existing gaps between the institutions [6] [7].

The work presented here addresses the study of phenomena associated with discontinuities and mathematical education in engineering. Discontinuities are associated to a transition between institutions (defined in a wide sense, see theoretical approach section). The starting point of our work is that we hypothesise that the path followed by engineering students' experiences what we could call a triple discontinuity (see Figure 1), making an analogy with Klein's famous double discontinuity. The first and third discontinuities are homologous to those announced by Klein in mathematics teacher education. The second is the one that would be more specific to engineering education: it is an internal discontinuity in engineering education institutions due to the transition between the mathematical courses for engineers and courses in engineering courses, in line with what has been observed in previous studies [8].

Fig. 1. Triple discontinuity in engineering education

1.2 Previous works

There are diverse works that have studied the differences in the mathematical activity existing in mathematics and in engineering courses. For example, González-Martín and Hernandez-Gomes [9] have studied the role of integrals in mathematics courses and in courses of mechanics of solids, in the same line, Hochmuth and Peters [10] conducted a study analysing the different discourses in mathematics and in signal theory courses. Both studies are framed within the ATD and mobilise the notion of praxeology [11] to model the existing mathematical activity in each course.

The first work developed to study our hypothesis was a qualitative study that allowed us to pilot an interview protocol addressed to both mathematics and engineering teachers at an engineering school in Barcelona (Spain). The study wanted to characterise the epistemological conception of these two positions: first-year mathematics teachers and engineering courses' teachers and to analyse to what extent these conceptions revealed a discontinuity [12].

The crucial fact that appeared as one of the main findings is that both mathematics and engineering teachers show an elevated level of consensus in the selection of the important contents in the fields of linear algebra and analysis. However, an analysis of statements of each collective reveals that under the "label" of "solving linear systems" or "finding the derivative of a function" the targeted activity is very different.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Our work is framed within the ATD initiated by Yves Chevallard during the decade of 1980s in the field of mathematics education but that has widely spread in the field of sciences and engineering education during the last 10 years. Particularly, in this work we use two theoretical developments of the ATD: the notions of *institution* (and institutional relativity of knowledge) and that of *praxeology*.

In the ATD an *institution* is any created reality of which people can be members (permanent or temporary). Accordingly, the group of teachers of engineering courses and the group of teachers of mathematics courses are institutions under the ATD conception. In addition, ATD considers that knowledge conception is institutional-dependent. In other words, in the same engineering school, the kind of activity existing in mathematics courses under the label "functions" differs heavily on what is considered under the same label in engineering courses.

The second notion is that of *praxeology*. To present the concept, we rely on this statement by Bosch and Gascón [13, p. 68]: "ATD postulates that any activity related to the production, diffusion, or acquisition of knowledge should be interpreted as an ordinary human activity, and thus proposes a general model of human activities built on this key notion of praxeology". A praxeology is formed by a quadruplet $[T/t/\theta/\Theta]$ consisting of a type of tasks to perform T , a technique t which allows the completion of the task, a discourse (technology) θ that explains and justifies the technique, and a theory Θ that includes the discourse. The praxeology consists of two blocks: the praxis block (including T and t) and the logos block (including θ and Θ).

Characterising the mathematical activity in praxeological terms allow us to detach from the knowledge described in terms of contents that in our previous work hid relevant differences between interviewees.

3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The research questions we address in our work are:

- RQ1: To what extent the modification of the initial interview protocol in terms of praxeologies allow us to characterise the differences in the epistemological conceptions of engineering and mathematics teachers?
- RQ2: Characterise and identify the characteristics of the 2nd discontinuity in engineering education through a qualitative study.

4 METHODOLOGY

4.1 Questionnaire and interviews design. From pilot to the final version.

We present a qualitative study that intends to characterise the internal discontinuity in the mathematical education in engineering degrees. The first step of this research was the work where the interview protocol was piloted [12]. In this work we figured out that the interviews were too long (more than 1h) and that the analysis of the answers revealed important differences at the level of the targeted activity while the selection of the contents showed up high levels of consensus. The structure of the interview was not able to make these differences emerge.

The original interview protocol had four sections (personal background, research background, mathematical elements, and their role in engineering subjects, and mathematical contents in the course taught).

In the new interview protocol, we have decided to split the interview in two parts to shorten the face-to-face interview: a first moment where the interviewee fills in an online survey and a second part of a semi-structured interview. The online survey has 4 sections:

1. Personal background (including research background)
2. Evaluation of the applicationist conception of mathematics education in engineering according to the work of Barquero and colleagues [14]. The characterisation of the applicationist conception is done through the level of agreement (5-level Likert scale) to five statements proposed in [14]. In addition, we allow the participants to add a short text field justifying their answer.
3. Mathematical contents in engineering: selection of common subjects in linear algebra and analysis in terms of relative importance (five level Likert scale ranging from “I do not consider it a critical content; it belongs to the 10% less relevant” to “I consider it a crucial content; it belongs to the 90% more relevant”)

4. Regarding the teaching activity. In the survey we asked the participants to choose one of the taught courses and to select the mathematical content that they consider as more relevant.

The semi-structured interviews had 4 sections. In the first one (1) we introduced explicitly to the interviewees the notions of praxeology, type of tasks and technique from the ATD. The interviewees were asked to describe the mathematical activity in these terms and to avoid the classical labels of contents to avoid the fake consensus found in the first edition. In the second section (2) we introduced two mathematical activities that had been proposed in first-year courses and we asked them to identify potential type of tasks and techniques that would emerge.

In the third section (3) the interviewee was confronted to the results of the third block of the online survey, and we asked them to describe the contents selected as more important in terms of type of task and techniques. Finally, the fourth block (4) the interviewees were asked to propose three types of tasks and techniques that they consider important but which they believe are absent in engineering education. The entire interviews are available at <https://sites.google.com/euss.cat/sefi2022>

4.2 Description of the interviewees and institutions of origin

The interviews were carried out at the Escola Universitarià Salesiana de Sarrià (EUSS) and the Institut Químic de Sarrià (IQS). Five engineering degrees are taught at EUSS (Electronics, Mechanics, Automotive, Industrial Organisation and Renewable Energies and Energy Efficiency) whereas IQS offers degrees in Chemistry, Chemical engineering, Biotechnology, Pharmacy, Biomedical Sciences and in Industrial engineering. Both Institutions are strongly interested in the implementation of teaching innovation processes and have extensive experience in this field.

Mathematics teaching in all EUSS degrees is concentrated in three subjects: two in the first year and one in the second one. Mathematics is offered in the first semester with 7 ECTS, calculus in the second semester with 8 ECTS and statistics in the fourth semester with 6 ECTS.

The distribution of mathematical content in the IQS depends to a greater extent on the degree programme studied, but if we focus on engineering studies, we can see that all three degrees (in Biotechnology, in Industrial Engineering and in Chemical Engineering) offer a 12 ECTS subject called mathematics during the first two semesters. Chemical engineering students also see a 6 ECTS course in computer science and numerical methods in semesters 1 and 2 and an additional 6 ECTS in applied statistics in semester 4. Biotechnology students take a 5 ECTS course in statistics in semester 4 whereas for industrial engineering students there is a 6 ECTS course in statistics in the 1st semester, and 2 courses of 4,5 ECTS each in the 3rd and 6th semester named mathematics II and III. The syllabi of each degree can be consulted in detail on the centre's websites: www.euss.cat or www.iqs.edu.

The first institution, formed by the group of teachers of mathematical courses, has the following profiles. The first mathematics teacher (MT1) has a degree and a PhD

in Mathematics and has always been involved in university teaching and research, with more than 30 years of experience. MT1 teaches mathematics, calculus, and statistics at EUSS. The second lecturer (MT2) has a degree and a PhD in Chemistry, and, except for a one-year break, he has always worked in the academic field, where he has been teaching for the last 9 years. He teaches mathematics and other engineering subjects. The third teacher (MT3) has a degree in Mathematics and a master's degree in Applied Mathematics. MT3 teaches mathematics, calculus and statistics and has more than 30 years of teaching experience. The fourth lecturer (MT4) is an Industrial Engineer with a PhD in Chemical Engineering with more than 18 years of teaching experience and involved now in mathematics II and physics teaching at IQS. The fifth one (MT5) has a Mathematics degree and is currently a doctoral student in Philosophy. MT5 has been teaching only for one year and he currently teaches mathematics I at IQS.

The second institution, made up of the teachers of engineering subjects, has the following profiles. The first teacher in the engineering field (ET1) has a degree in Physics and holds a PhD in Materials Engineering. She has always worked in the field of research and university teaching in the degree of Mechanical Engineering, specifically in the field of strength of materials, elasticity, and structures. ET2 holds a PhD in Telecommunication Engineering and after his doctorate he worked for a short period in industry and then returned to research in supercomputing. He currently teaches in the degree of Electronic Engineering, specifically in the field of industrial computing and communications. ET3 is a Mechanical Engineer and holds a PhD in Material Science. He started his professional career as a laboratory technician and ended up developing a PhD in Biomaterials. He teaches in all the school's degrees in the field of materials, manufacturing processes and strength of materials. ET4 has a degree in Industrial Organisation and a PhD in Business. He only teaches on the school's Industrial Organisation Engineering degree. His professional career has always been in academia, and he teaches strategic management and quantitative methods for management. ET5 is an engineer with a PhD in Civil Engineering. She has developed her professional career in academia and teaches in all degree programs, specifically in physics, strength of materials, machines and mechanisms and fluids. ET6 has a degree and a PhD in Marine Sciences. After a period of 9 years in the field of research and university, he worked for 7 years in industry, as a consultant, as data Analyst and modelling expert. He come back to the University 4 years ago, teaching in all the school's degrees in the field of electrical physics, manufacturing processes and fluid engineering.

4.3 Analysis of results: surveys and thematic analysis

The results of the online survey have been analysed qualitatively while the interviews have been fully transcribed and will be analysed using deductive thematic analysis [15].

The deductive coding is based in the identification of different types of tasks and techniques and their justification. Specifically, includes the identification of the

following themes: (1) paper-and-pencil techniques, (2) computer-based techniques, (3) calculator-based techniques, (4) research-based techniques, (5) tasks involving the solution of short mathematical exercises, (6) tasks involving contextualized mathematical exercise, (7) tasks involving the use of engineering models, (8) justification based on cognitive effects on students, (9) justification based on the application, (10) justification as a way to introduce engineering models. The thematic analysis is now being conducted and only partial results will be presented in this paper.

5 RESULTS

5.1 Online questionnaire

The main results of the online survey reveal important differences between the mathematics and the engineering teachers in diverse items. Regarding the second block, that related with the applicationist, one of the differences that appear concerns the conception of mathematics as a tool to be used in engineering courses. The positions to the statement “A relatively deep study of engineering phenomena and models could be done without using mathematics” are very different in mathematics and engineering teachers. While mathematics teachers fully disagree, considering that any study of engineering phenomena could be done without mathematics, engineering teachers have a less consensual position. For example, ET6 complements her answer with the following statement: “many engineering phenomena or models can be understood without a deep understanding of the mathematics backing them” (translation by the authors).

Another interesting aspect where the answers between engineering and mathematics teachers diverge is about the position on the following statement: “In education, mathematics is generally introduced independently of physical or engineering systems that can be modelled mathematically.” Engineering teachers show full agreement on that: for example, ET1 states: “Mathematics are treated as an entity of their own, detached from other disciplines. At most, they are presented as a tool, but just as detached from the other disciplines” (translation by the authors). However, mathematics teachers present less consensus and one (MT2) states that “it is necessary to learn some mathematical mechanisms and concepts in order to apply them in engineering courses. I think that application examples in each chapter might help...” (translation by the authors).

In the third block of the online survey, where participants had to prioritize a list of contents, the level of agreement is very high, in coherence with what was already observed in the piloting survey. Solving Linear Systems with Matrices, Derivation and Integration are the contents considered as more important in both groups. These results, again, are very close to the previously obtained during the piloting of the study.

5.2 Interviews

As said before, the full coding of the transcripts is still in process, and we will present, for now only preliminary data. One of the main goals to introduce the notion of type of tasks and technique to the interviewees was to make the description of the mathematical activity more explicit. The introduction of the notions was clear enough to all of the interviewees and after the first block no one showed any problem when describing mathematical activity in praxeological terms.

Regarding the second block of the interview, it seems that some differences appeared. For the first activity, the type of tasks identified were the same: “find the derivative of the function”, “solve the equation of the derivative equal to zero”, “find the second derivative”, etc. Regarding the techniques, both groups of teachers identified similar techniques and both groups assign paper-and-pencil techniques to the first-year courses while allow other techniques in engineering courses. For example, ET6 stated: “in first-years mathematics, they would find the derivative by-hand, using derivation rules, however in engineering subjects we would never do that, and we would use a calculator or maybe an online symbolic calculator...”. Other statements from mathematics teachers showed up these differences: “in first -year courses we would calculate derivatives and solve the equations using paper-and-pencil...but I am quite sure that in other courses, the students would graph the function using google...”.

Concerning the second activity (about population growth) and with an inquiry-based approach, the answers start to diverge between the two groups. ET1 stated, for example that considers that this second activity “allow to show mathematics involved with other disciplines, such as biology to solve a real or close-to-reality problem”. In a very close line, ET6 states that the students would mobilize tasks that do not appear usually in the first-year mathematics at her institution. She highlighted the data analysis, forecasting and validation of the results against a real setting.

When the teachers were asked about the type of tasks and techniques that do not appear in the mathematics courses, it is particularly interesting the answer of MT4; he is aware of the prominence of the algorithmic approach in their courses (paper-and-pencil work) but he considers that it is a matter of resources. He states: “I think that the manual calculation can have a value for itself, but I am aware that devoting more time to work with modelling would be better for engineering training...however I cannot see how to make a lot of students work on modelling...the mechanical work is a way to deal with a big number of students”. Another mathematical teacher states (MT5) that “I think that in engineering the students see very little algebra, however, I do not really know to what extent what algebra is needed for engineers...”.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The first analysis of the results, especially the interviews transcripts, show that the interviewees are able to describe the mathematical activity (existing and desired) in terms of type of tasks and techniques. This fact allows us to, at least partially, answer RQ1. The statements and the discourse analysed to the point confirm that

the modification of the survey and of the protocol overcomes the limitation of describing mathematical knowledge in terms of contents. We hope that the further analysis of the data will help to make differences and similarities between groups emerge.

Regarding the second question we only can answer it preliminary using data from the online survey. The results obtained and their justifications seem to indicate that there is an important level of consensus on the important contents to be taught in first-year courses. However, some differences appear in the applicationist conception and its justification. Mathematics teachers seem to agree on a conception where mathematics are a tool to be applied in engineering courses, engineering teachers see mathematics as an intrinsic component of engineering. This dependency between mathematics and engineering models is not coherent with the detachment between mathematics and engineering courses.

Further analysis work will be conducted, incorporating more data with participants from other engineering schools in order to validate this preliminary results.

References

- [1] C. Winberg, S. Winberg, C. Jacobs, J. Garraway and P. Engel-Hills, "I take engineering with me': epistemological transitions across an engineering curriculum," *Teaching in Higher Education*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 398-414, 2016.
- [2] G. Gueudet, M. Bosch, A. A. di Sessa, O. N. Kwon and L. Verschaffel, *Transitions in Mathematics Education*, Springer Cham, 2016.
- [3] F. Klein, *Elementarmathematik vom höheren Standpunkte aus*, London: Macmillan, 1908.
- [4] V. McGhie, "Entering university studies: identifying enabling factors for a successful transition from school to university," *Higher Education*, vol. 73, no. 3, pp. 407-422, 2017.
- [5] J. Andrews, R. Clark and G. Knowles, "From opportunity to reality: transition into engineering education, trauma or transformation?," *European Journal of Engineering Education*, pp. 807-820, 2017.
- [6] P. Kent and R. Noss, "Mathematics in the university education of engineers," The Ove Aurup Foundation, London, 2003.
- [7] S. R. Brunhaver, R. Korte, S. R. Barley and S. D. Sheppard, "Bridging the gaps between engineering education and practice," in *U.S. Engineering in a Global Economy*, R. B. Freeman and H. Salzman, Eds., Chicago, University of Chicago Press, 2018, pp. 129-163.
- [8] A. Romo-Vázquez, *La formation mathématique des futurs ingénieurs (Doctoral Dissertation)*, Université Paris 7, 2009.
- [9] A. González-Martín and G. Hernandez-Gomes, "The graph of a function and its antiderivative: a praxeological analysis in the context of Mechanics of Solids for engineering.," in *Proceedings of the Eleventh Congress of the European Society for Research in Mathematics Education*, Utrecht, 2019.
- [10] R. Hochmuth and J. Peters, "About the "Mixture" of Discourses in the Use of Mathematics in Signal Theory," *Educação Matemática Pesquisa*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 454-471, 2020.
- [11] Y. Chevallard, "La recherche en didactique et la formation des professeurs: problématiques.," in *Actes de la X école d'été de didactique des mathématiques*, Houlgate, IUFM de l'académie de Caen, 2000, pp. 98-112.
- [12] A. Authors, "----," ---, pp. ---, 2022.
- [13] M. Bosch and J. Gascón, "Introduction to the anthropological theory of the didactic (ATD)," in *Networking of theories as a research practice in mathematics education*, Switzerland, Springer, 2014, pp. 67-83.

- [14] B. Barquero, M. Bosch and J. Gascón, "Incidencia del "aplicacionismo" en la integración de la modelización matemática en la enseñanza universitaria de las ciencias experimentales," *Enseñanza de las ciencias: revista de investigación y experiencias didácticas*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 83-100, 2014.
- [15] J. Fereday and E. Muir-Cochrane, "Demonstrating Rigor Using Thematic Analysis: A Hybrid Approach of Inductive and Deductive Coding and Theme Development," *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 80-92, 2006.